

REFERENCES

1. Jalolov J.J. Chet tili o'qitish metodikasi: chet tillar oliy o'quv yurtlari (fakultetlari) talabalari uchun darslik. — Toshkent: O'qituvchi, 2012.
2. Воробьева Е.И., Макковеева Ю.А., Ушакова Н.Л. Современные методы обучения иностранным языкам. — Архангельск, 2019.
3. Жалолов Жамол Жалолович, Махкамова Гульнара Турдахуновна, Ашуров Шахобиддин Саидович. Методика преподавания английского языка (теория и практика). — Ташкент: Узбекистан, 2014.

THE ROLE OF FEEDBACK IN DEVELOPING COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCE IN PRIMARY SCHOOL LEARNERS

Bakhramova Ayimjon Sherzadovna

3rd year student of Uzbekistan State World Languages University,
English Philology faculty, Tashkent

***Abstract.** This article discusses the role of giving feedback to young language learners to improve their communicative competence. The author highlights four components and explains several ways how to improve learners' ability to understand language effectively to communicate in authentic social and school environments.*

***Keywords.** Feedback, schoolchildren, competence, social, develop, primary, communicative competence.*

Introduction. It is known that effective feedback fosters development gives guidance, and opens windows and new opportunities. In addition, the descriptive nature of feedback has a lot more potential and positive effect on the teacher-student relationship than traditional assessment. In addition, giving and receiving feedback can be considered the starting point of reflection. Communicative competence is considered a holistic system of mental and behavioural characteristics of a person that contribute to successful communication, that is,

Languages, culture, and translation in modern linguistics: comparative approaches

achieving the goal (effective) and emotionally favorable (psychologically comfortable) for the parties involved. From the standpoint of dialogue and interaction, the leading socio-psychological needs and value orientations of primary schoolchildren are shown; their communicative difficulties are described. Technologies and criteria of efficiency of development of communicative competences are presented: paired and group work, tasks aimed at independent search and choice of solutions, the justification of opinions; problem communicative situations (cases); games; special communicative tasks, etc.

Feedback refers to commentary, verbal or written information that a student receives about their performance. In the academic environment, feedback is an essential component and a vital strategy of the teaching-learning process. If there is an assessment in the teaching-learning process, then there is feedback, and it is given in different forms to the students. Helping students to learn from their activities, mainly through encouraging dialogue, is a crucial aspect of feedback.

Feedback is central to the development of effective educational practice and the students' perceptions of the practices of feedback have an impact on the fruitfulness of the teaching-learning process. The students' perceptions, understanding of the purpose, and beliefs about feedback are crucial determinants for achieving educational outcomes. In the absence of meaningful feedback, good practices are not reinforced, poor performance is not corrected, and the path to improvement is not identified. Effective feedback starts a thought process for students as it allows them to evaluate the quality of their work against that of their teacher or peers and empowers them to become self-regulated learners which effectively improves their learning abilities, for feedback to be effective it should be timely and relate to the focus of the learning; it needs to acknowledge where the student has been successful and identify where and how improvement can take place. It also needs to be able to be clearly understood by the student, allowing them the time needed for improvement (Chomsky1957). The feedback given becomes useful when it is provided quickly enough and acted upon to improve student's work and learning. The feedback should be of value to the student by

'closing the gap' on their. Understanding and providing an opportunity for dialogue to occur. (Ivanov. D.2003.) At the educational level, to be able to acquire oral competence would be necessary a continued practice of the oral expression, from the infancy up to the conclusion of the studies, adapted to the age of the pupils. The school must develop in the pupil this capacity and evaluate it since the current society demands interactions that need the oral expression in public.

Although there has been more effort to develop the written competence at education, nowadays the communicative approach and the orality has been more considered. It is not very sure nevertheless that this change has overcome the simple abstract level of the definition of aims and of the good desires to reach the level of real changes in the practices in each of the educational levels. Communicative competence is integrated by four competencies: linguistics, sociolinguistics, strategic and discursive (Marss 2016. p. 7). In our case we focus on the oral part that includes, mainly the four mentioned competencies.

Conclusion. Without feedback, communication is nothing more than information. This makes feedback the primary component in the communication process because it allows the sender to analyze the effect of the message. It helps the sender ensure that the recipient has interpreted the message correctly. Communicative competence is understood as a complex of personal characteristics that involves orientation in various communication situations, based on the knowledge and sensory experience of the individual; the ability to interact with others, understand oneself and other people with the constant modification of mental states, interpersonal relationships and social conditions.

REFERENCES

1. Abatihun Alehegn Sewagegn. Feedback in Primary Schools: Students' Perceptions of the Practice»

2. Amrein-Beardsley, A., & Holloway, J. (2017). Value-added models for teacher evaluation and accountability: Commonsense assumptions, *Educational Policy*, 33(3), 516-542.
3. Ballou, D., & Springer, M. G. (2015). Using student test scores to measure teacher performance. *Educational Researcher*, 44(2), 77-86.
4. Ballou, D., Sanders, W., & Wright, P. (2004). Controlling for student background in value-added assessment of teachers. *Journal of Educational and Behavioral Statistics*, 29(1), 37-65.
<https://doi.org/10.3102/10769986029001037>

THE THEORY OF PROBLEM-SOLVING TASKS IN TEACHING TO THE PRIMARY LEARNERS

Bakhramova Iroda

Student, UzSWLU, English Philology Faculty

Tashkent, Uzbekistan

irodaakhrorovna@gmail.com

***Abstract.** This article explores the specific features of problem-solving activities and their importance for primary school students. Problem-solving activities help children develop critical thinking, self-confidence, and the ability to express freely their opinions on events that they may encounter in learning foreign languages. In addition, conducting problem-solving activities with a large group of children helps them develop teamwork and listening skills objectives.*

***Keywords.** Problem-solving, critical thinking, features, activities, teamwork, primary school, conduct, ability, importance.*

Introduction: In the educational process, skills such as critical thinking and problem-solving are aimed at helping primary school children easily learn lessons, especially new languages. Working with children who have independent thinking and can find solutions to any problem has a great impact on the teacher, making